

Fourth year internship report

Julien Bourget

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**“ERGONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF AN
ACTIVE ORTHOSIS FOR PARKINSON’S
DISEASE PATIENTS”**

“NIATS – Universidade Federal
de Uberlândia”

Internship supervisor: Adriano O. Andrade
School supervisor: Norbert Noury

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Introduction: problem and work objectives

Parkinson's disease is a disease which affects more than 6 million people in the world, making it the second most spread neurodegenerative disease, easily beaten by Alzheimer and its 48 million victims.

During the last seven years my professor, Mr. Andrade, studied the problem. Without seeking to cure the disease itself, for it is not the matter of his research, he considered the idea to improve the patient's daily life by developing a device to help them regain amplitude while performing movements of the wrist. Indeed, muscular rigidity caused by the disease prevents parkinsonian from moving freely their joints. The wrist being a direct access to the hand, and therefore, to our surrounding environment, focusing on it sure is a lead that deserves to be studied.

Before starting, let's begin by a quick overview of the disease.

I. Parkinson's disease

Parkinson's disease is a neurodegenerative disease that affects the central nervous system, causing motor and neuropsychiatric disturbances [1].

Motor symptoms are well-know for most of them. Four main are identified: tremor, bradykinesia, muscular rigidity and postural instability.

Usually affecting the limbs' extremities, like the hand, tremor can disappear during deep stages of sleep. It can nonetheless spread to other parts of the body, like the jaw. Bradykinesia, also known as slowless of movement, alters the initiation and the execution of this last, essentially by making movement sequential, discontinued. Muscular rigidity is caused by an increase of the muscle tone, which is no other than an involuntary contraction of the muscles, at the origin of pains. To finish, postural instability makes its appearance in the later stages of the process and is responsible for losses of balance and falls, whose consequences can be bone fractures.

Neurophychiatric symptoms are as numerous and as annoying. Among them, we identify disorders of cognition, mood, behavior and thought, with some rare cases of dementia.

Cognition disorders concerns mainly executive dysfunction (which is a disruption of cognitive processes whose role is to regulate and control other cognitive processes) and cognitive flexibility (the ability to switch between two concepts while thinking or having a conversation). Cognition disorders also affect control of attention, memory and perception of time. Mood alterations refer to depression, apathy and anxiety, respectively responsible for sadness, loss of self-confidence and aversion, for a lack of feeling as well as a complete disinterest of the rest of the world, and for a permanent state of nervousity.

To this day, no cure is available, for the causes of the disease remain unknown. It is believed it is a combinaison of genetic and environmental factors. Indeed,

mutations of the genes SNCA and LRRK-2 (among others) would lead to the apparition of the symptoms described previously. Moreover, being in contact with pesticides could play a role as well. But as surprising as it may seem, smoking would lower the risks to be subject to Parkinson's disease.

It was also noticed the decrease of the level of dopamine production by the brain due to the motor symptoms. Patients are then usually prescribed levodopa, which is converted into dopamine once it reaches the brain.

Parkinson's disease is thereby very annoying for patients, for it affects the body and the brain. It makes impossible to maintain physical integrity, creates in some cases dependence, and alters the behaviour itself. Hundreds of researchers are studying the disease, without completely understanding it yet. But as it is not conceivable to wait for a solution that may only arrive in numerous years (not to say never), solutions must be brought in order to improve the patient's daily life. Here comes Mr. Andrade and his idea.

II. Mr. Andrade's project

In 2011, Mr. Andrade has the idea to develop an active orthosis to help the parkinsonians wrist rehabilitation.

Made of aluminium, the orthosis is designed to be worn on the forearm. It must be seen as a training device, a rehabilitation tool to help patients regain amplitude in the movement of the wrist. For this, it is composed of a handle where the patient places the palm of his/her hand and of a main structure on which is secured a linear DC-motor. This last can actuate, if supplied and programmed, the sliding of a main central axis. The purpose is to provide a mechanical assistance to the performing of flexions and extensions by the patients. The motor is here to ensure the device is usable by everyone, and ensuring its good programming will constitute one of my objectives. The whole device weights 900g and is still, to this day, a prototype.

Figure 1 : Orthosis placed on the forearm

III. My role

At my arrival, I was informed of the flaws of the orthosis. Reaching perfection may be impossible, but approaching it is not. Still, in our case, we were far from perfection. Far enough so that the orthosis wasn't in a state where it could pretend to be used. Indeed, one thing I have been informed of was its stability problem. During its use by my professor, students or myself, the orthosis oscillated from right to left on the forearm. More than being uncomfortable, it made all results of any potential experiment unreliable, for we aimed at having patients using the orthosis. It is planned that during training sessions and exercises, sensors (inertial ones) and electrodes will be placed on patients, to assess their starting situation and observe improvements day after day. This follow-up must be rigorous.

It is important to keep in mind the device is still to this day a prototype, certainly improved, but a prototype, nonetheless. And we have no guarantee it will prove to be effective. But to maximise the chances of success, we had to propose a device as reliable as possible.

In this context, I had first described my mission as follows: to contribute to the development of an orthosis to enable persons suffering from Parkinson's disease to regain amplitude in the movement of the wrist, to improve their daily life.

During the first three weeks of my internship my professor was absent, I managed to start studying the orthosis by myself, to propose improvements, to take some initiatives. But I couldn't afford doing whatever I wanted without his expertise.

Samila, a master's student supervised my work during this period and this, until the end along with Mr. Andrade after he returned. She gave me advices and helped me leading the experiments.

Thus, after a month or so, my mission became clearer. Its purpose hadn't changed, but the tasks it implied had become more explicit. I had identified variables we were facing problems with, and determined others that had to be improved and/or assessed. Here then, is the entitle of my intership: "Identify the main variables of the orthosis susceptible to defect, to propose improvements and to assess these lasts, in order to make the orthosis a reliable and ergonomic device".

The variables it is refered to are:

- 1) Stability
- 2) The motion amplitude alteration by the device
- 3) Inertia
- 3.bis) The relative inertia
- 4) The ideal position of use

Apart from the study of the variables presented, it will be made mention in this report of my participation in the writing of a conference paper for the World Congress on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering, which takes place this year in June. This paper aimed at presenting Mr. Andrade's work which hadn't been published so far.

The laboratory

I. The location

I did my internship in Brazil, in the city of Uberlândia where I stayed four months and a half. Located in the state of Minas Gerais, at the north of the state of São Paulo, it is its second biggest city behind the capital Belo Horizonte, may it be by its number of inhabitants (around 660 000) or by its economical activity.

I was part of the UFU (Universidade Federal de Uberlândia), and more especially of the NIATS (Núcleo de Inovação e Avaliação Tecnológica em Saúde), The Center for Innovation and Technology assessment. The university is a public institution and counts around 22000 students split up into three campuses, into various courses : mainly in engineering, medicine, architecture, physical education, physics, art and literature.

II. The NIATS

The center for Innovation and Technology Assessment is a research group of the UFU recognised by the Ministry of Health. It is part of the Brazilian Network for Health Assessment (REBRATS) since 2012 [2].

The mission of the group is to develop, evaluate and compare technologies in healthcare that can be used in clinical practice.

The laboratory counts five main areas of research :

- 1) Health Technology Assessment: evaluation of the clinical and technical performances of new or already existing electro-medical technologies
- 2) Biomedical Signal Processing: modelisation and analyse of biological systems
- 3) Biomechanics: development and use of systems for the monitoring and the evaluation of human movement
- 4) Telemedicine: conception of systems that allow the remote monitoring of biological information
- 5) Medical Imaging: technologies devoted to control and diagnostic through image processing

The laboratory is composed of various profiles going from undergraduate students to researchers. One of them is currently at the head of the group: Mr. Adriano Oliveira Andrade, who was no other than my supervisor during the internship.

Adriano is a Brazilian researcher aged of 42. He first graduated in electrical engineering before pursuing by doing a doctorate where he studies cybernetics. He directs his researches on biomedical signal processing and modelling, and assistive technologies. Then comes his interest in Parkinson's disease and the development of the device he is now working on.

He is currently at the head of the faculty's first cycle biomedical engineering department (for undergraduate students), and president of the SBEB (Sociedade Brasileira de Engenharia Biomédica for Brazilian Society of Biomedical Engineering).

The laboratory can of course rely on partners throughout Brazil to meet the needs of the National Health System, like the Clinical Hospital of Uberlândia or the Laboratory of Sensory Motor Rehabilitation, of the University of Vale do Paraíba. But it also counts lots of institution located abroad, like the Institute of Biomedical Engineering of the University of New Brunswick, Canada, the Cybernetics Research Group of the University of Reading UK or again the Laboratoire d'Automatique Humaine et de Sciences Comportementales of the University of Lorraine, France.

Apart from Mr. Adriano's work we will soon say more about, the NIATS also houses various projects, whose majority deals with Parkinson's disease. For instance, one of them consists in monitoring motor symptoms of the disease in the long term using non-invasive sensors to assess the efficiency of the treatments patients receive. For this, the study plans to equip them with light gloves containing the sensors, designed not to bother them in their usual tasks. This aims at detecting symptoms that may not occur during detection sessions.

Parkinson's disease did become the number one study subject of the laboratory. Everyone tries his best to propose improvements to the already existing detection technique, or to propose new devices to improve patient's everyday life.

MISSION 1: The stability of the device

I. Introduction

As I started to mention it in the introduction, the device was unstable. This is the default that is the most obvious to notice, and the most annoying as well. Oscillations from right to left occurred during the use of the device, which implied the orthosis was no longer in the axis of the forearm while flexions and extensions were performed. The main consequence would have been the alteration of the data we had planned to acquire on patients.

II. First ideas

I quickly realised the problem came from the fact the main structure of the orthosis, its body, did not wrap the whole limb. Indeed, the inferior part of the device was (and is still) "empty". Nothing ensures the junction between the lower extremities of the structure as you can see on the picture below:

Figure 2 : Orthosis viewed from the back

Being maintained with velcro, this last had nothing to exert pressure on, generating the sensation of loosening. Considering this, I tried to erase this loose.

The first solution which was considered was to change the structure of the orthosis itself. Being made of metal, it is hard but not impossible to give it the shape we want by bending it to « fill », or at least to reduce the gap. My professor was absent at this moment, and he wouldn't necessarily be glad to find back something he had worked so many years on completely different because of a new intern he hardly knew. Moreover, I had no guarantee the structure could still fit someone's forearm. So, I quickly gave up the idea.

Another idea was considered: to cover the inside of the structure with something swellable. Basically, a brassard, of the same kind that the ones used to measure arterial tension. This way, we would just have had to swell the brassard

at our convenience until the loose is erased. As one was about to be ordered, a last idea came to my mind, which ended up being the chosen one: filling the gap.

III. The 3D-support

The idea came when I saw in another laboratory of the university (the Biolab) a 3D printer (from the CubeX company). Printing the support in 3D was a good option, for it avoided having to need the help of a specialist, reduced the costs and obtaining duration as well. The piece we desired wasn't very sophisticated, so I managed to do it myself.

Necessary dimensions of the orthosis were taken, and the ones of the support were chosen accordingly to fit the device. Moreover, it had to have a thin and flat layer at its basis (3mm) to ensure solidity and had of course to adapt itself to the shape of forearm. A tiny length (3mm again) had to exceed the orthosis as well, to prevent the support from sliding inside the structure of the orthosis, where it would have become ineffective. The following table reports the dimensions:

	Dimensions of the orthosis	Dimensions of the support
Length	12.0 cm	12.6 cm
Front width	6.3 cm	6.9 cm
Back width	9.0 cm	9.6 cm

Table 1 : Dimensions of the orthosis and its support

Autodesk and Blender were some of the considered softwares to design the piece, but this was before the discovering of Tinkercad whose description can be found in annex 1.

Once the piece was designed, Biolab kindly allowed us the access to the printer. After seven laborious failures encountered because of heat problems, the eighth attempt turned out to be a success. The result is displayed below:

Figure 3 : 3D model before and after printing

IV. The assesement of the support

The next step was to determine whether the support was making the device more stable or not. Based on our first impressions, we could feel it did help to maintain the whole structure and that oscillations were reduced. But an objective assessment had to be carried out.

The idea was then to quantify the increase of stability provided by the support. We had at our disposal inertial sensors and a software my professor developed, especially dedicated to their use. The way to proceed was then simple, to compare stability with, and without the support.

1. Tremsen and the inertial sensors

To apprehend the experiment in good conditions, it is essential to understand the functioning of the tool we had:

a) Tremsen

Tremsen (National Institute of Intellectual Property-Brazil-BR 10 2014 023282) is the name given both to a software and a hardware developed in order to propose objective assessment tools of signals acquired in a study context of Parkinson's disease. Its purpose is to acquire and to display data in real time. For this, the hardware is composed of two inertial channels of acquisition, each one handling two inertial measurement units (the name given to a device composed of an accelerometer¹ and a gyroscope²), each being coupled here with a magnetometer³. It also disposes of two channels especially dedicated to EMG signals (electromyographic signals) to measure muscular electrical activity. The hardware filters and amplifies the signal before the software displays it. This last offers various parameters the user can set, as the acquisition duration time or the sensor's measurement range. Data are exported to the txt format.

b) Inertial measurement unit and accelerometer

An inertial measurement unit is a sensor in fact composed of two sensors: an accelerometer and a gyroscope. To lead our experiment, we chose to focus only on the accelerometer because as everyone knows, position, which is what we aimed determining to compare lateral positions, arises from speed, itself arising from acceleration.

An accelerometer is a sensor enabling the measure of a linear acceleration. But often confusion is made with the name. Most of the accelerometers sold nowadays enable a three-axis detection, to enable a detection in all the dimensions of space. But these three-axis accelerometers are composed of three linear accelerometers, each one being sensitive to variations occurring in one direction only. Therefore, it is more accurate to speak about a three-axis accelerometer.

Acceleration is usually expressed in g (for gravity), worth $9,81 \text{ m.s}^{-2}$.

¹ ST Microelectronics, Ref LSM303DLM

² ST Microelectronics, Ref L3G4200D

³ ST Microelectronics, Ref LSM303DLM

Accelerometers are found in numerous applications, and enable measures of shocks, vibrations and movements. In most cases, they are used to determine the angle of inclination between the surface of the earth and the device on which it is placed.

As any sensor they have common characteristics like the range of measure, the bandwidth, and of course specific ones like the linear acceleration sensitivity, the number of axis, or the zero-g level (the offset).

Several types of accelerometers exist, based on their physical principle of functioning, like the piezoelectric or the piezoresistive ones. Ours is a capacitive one and belongs to MEMS's family (Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems). It measures acceleration by change of capacitance [3]. For each axis, we have a mass attached to springs and fixed outer plates. The mass is compelled to move in only one direction, as shown in figure 4. When an acceleration is applied, the capacitance between the mass and the plates changes. This last is measured, processed to correspond to a specific acceleration value.

Figure 4 : Functioning principle of a capacitive accelerometer – Dejan Nedelkovski, How to Mechatronics

2. The protocol and the data collection

Before making any acquisition, a protocol had to be written (see in annex 2), describing the motive of our experiment, the problem, the tools we had at our disposal, the way we intended to collect and process the data.

Tremesen was used. A sensor was placed on the orthosis. A healthy subject (me...) carried out the experiment as described in the protocol. The purpose was to compare the impact of the piece printed in 3D. We knew oscillations were lateral and then identified on which axis of the three-axis accelerometer the oscillations were occurring, to extract the relevant data.

3. Data processing and results

To process the data, Matlab was chosen. Another software, like R, could have suited as well but Matlab contains by default all the tools one needs to process signals. A brief description of the software is given in annex 3 [4].

The signals we imported from Tremsen were at the .txt format. They contained the raw accelerations. When we visualised them, I noticed a slight inclinaison over time, especially for the ones where the support was not used. My teacher informed me it was the result of a trend, and that it had to be removed.

a) *A word about detrending*

A trend is a non-constant artefact that changes the mean of the signal over time. The amplitude of the signal is not altered, but its values are.

In our case, the accelerometer was also sensitive to involuntary movements I did while carrying out the acquisitions. These last induced trends. Gravity, which is an acceleration, was detected by the sensor as well. Therefore, the relevant values, the accelerations generated by the desired movements only, were not accessible directly.

Trends can be linear, or polynomial. In our case, they were both. To have an overview of the phenomenon, we adjusted in the figure displayed below a polynomial curve of order 1 (equivalent to a linear curve), and one of order 6 for the polynomial one (this order was chosen because it matches well the signal's profile). Here is what we obtained:

Figure 5 : Trends on one of the acquisitions without support

As we can see first, the signal's mean is not equal to 0 and varies over time, as the linear trend shows it well. Consequently, the data processing can provide wrong results, for the values it may work on are not relevant.

To remove this, there is technique called "*detrending*", which consists in "correcting" the signal by removing the trend. Its principle is simple: subtract a fitting curve (or the mean of the data) from the original data.

b) The steps

We had at our disposal five acquisitions performed without the support, and five with. Key steps of the scripts are given in annex 4. Signals were processed by pairs (one acquisition with the support with an acquisition without), but the steps described below were applied on each one independently:

- 1) Linear detrending
- 2) Polynomial detrending on the signal obtained after step 1
- 3) Double integration

Matlab proposes a function *detrend* I discovered once I had finished the writing and the processing of the data... Nonetheless we managed to produce something equivalent by creating a polynomial fitting curve (function *polyfit*), extracting the values of the curve (function *polyval*) that we then subtracted to the original data.

After the third step, here is an illustration of what we obtained for the first set of acquisitions:

Figure 6 : From the raw acceleration to the displacement (step 1 to 3)

In this case, we notice the trend mentioned previously for the raw acceleration without support, and the larger amplitude of displacement when the support is absent, which was expected.

What we did subsequently was considering two sets of data: the first one composed of the five acquisitions performed with the support, and the second one of the five acquisitions performed without. What for? To determine, for each set of data, its mean (called "average" in step 5 to avoid confusion) and the standard error of this mean: in other words, its dispersion. These dispersions enabled the estimation of two intervals of displacement from which were deduced two ranges of displacement. We compared them, to conclude on the efficiency of the support.

Then, four steps remained:

4) Calculation of the mean and of the standard deviation of each displacement (respectively with the functions *mean* and *std*)

5) Calculation of the mean of the means (that we called average).

Standard deviations being errors, their mean was calculated as follows:

$$m_{std} = \frac{1}{n} \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^n \sigma_i^2}$$

With:

σ_i the standard deviation of the record i

n the number of samples, five here

We now manipulated two sets of data. Step 6 was applied for each one:

6) Calculation of the standard error and of the interval of displacement of the device from which is deduced the range of displacement of the device

The standard error (SE) arises from m_{std} [5]:

$$SE = \frac{m_{std}}{\sqrt{n-1}}$$

7) Relative comparison between the two results obtained step 6. This last is expressed as a rate of change:

$$\text{Relative change of amplitude} = \frac{RD_{\text{without}} - RD_{\text{with}}}{RD_{\text{without}}} * 100$$

With RD_{without} and RD_{with} , respectively the range of displacement without the support, and with the support.

The table below displays all the results we obtained at each step, as well as the relative change of amplitude which serves as a conclusion.

	Mean with support (mm)	Std with support (mm)	Mean without support (mm)	Std without support (mm)
Record 1	6	13	15	39
Record 2	17	14	-4	31
Record 3	-2	18	-47	100
Record 4	22	19	-14	117
Record 5	12	21	15	41
Average (Avg)	11	7.7	-7	33.4
Standard error (SE)				
	3.9		16.7	
Avg - SE	7.1		-23.7	
Avg + SE	14.9		9.7	
Interval of displacement	[7.1; 14.9]		[-23.7; 9.7]	
Range of displacement	7.7		33.4	
Relative difference (%)	76.9			

Table 2 : Results of the data processing

V. Conclusion

Solving the stability issue was the number one priority, for no further experiment could have been led with a device providing results we would have known wrong due to transverse oscillations.

As table 2 shows it, transverse oscillations were reduced by 76.9%. The support then proved to be an efficient way to improve stability. Besides, based on people's feedback about the use of the support, comfort was improved as well. According to Mr. Andrade, this improvement was significant, significant enough so that we could now focus on the other variables.

With :

Letter	Length (cm)	Meaning
L	Modifiable (9,1 here)	Length of the junction between the handle and the attach of the axis of the actuator
a	12,3	Total length of the axis of the actuator
a ₁	Variable	Length between the attach of the axis of the actuator and the actuator
a ₂	Variable	Length between the actuator and the end of its axis
b	4,8	Length of the actuator

Table 3 : Signification of the letters used on figure 9

The central axis is represented in red on the figure. Its length doesn't change during movement, it remains equal to a_1+b+a_2 . Indeed, if a_1 increases, a_2 decreases, the same goes for the contrary.

With simple calculations (done in annex 5), I showed my professor we had to change the axis. How? By determining the length, it should have to enable a complete movement. Without much surprise, the result showed the current axis was not appropriate. It had to be at least 17,5 cm long.

By chance, a second axis was in our possession... of 18 cm! No need to order a new one and to wait for its arrival. The axis was then changed.

Figure 8 : Orthosis with the original axis, and with the new one

0,7 cm of the axis are covered with a plastic sheath (see in figure 8 above) and can't thereby slide in the actuator and contribute to the movement, which left us with an « effective axis » of $18 - 0,7 = 17,3 \text{ cm}$.

Here, something important must be specified. The reason why we focused on the amplitude and not on the angles of flexions and extensions separately is because the amplitude depends on no reference. Let me explain. From a patient to another, the orthosis won't be placed at the same place on the forearm, because every patient's forearm is different.

If, for a same patient, the orthosis is placed closer to the wrist then further, the angles of flexions will be different from each other, the same goes for the angles of extension. Why? Because the lengths a_1 and a_2 (shown in figure 7) are dependent on the rest position (the starting position). For example, if the orthosis

is closer to the wrist, a_1 will tend to be smaller, a_2 longer and therefore, α_{flex} more important.

If now, we consider the amplitude, the rest position does not impact anymore, for we only consider the sum of the absolute values of the angles the wrist can reach.

Apart from what has been said, the change of the axis was done soon. All the experiments that followed were done with the new axis.

III. Assessment of the wrist's amplitude alteration by the orthosis

With this new axis, it was time to see if the orthosis still altered the movement. I first wanted to use a goniometer and to measure manually. But I was suggested to use cameras to have a visual feedback and to ensure a better precision, cameras dedicated to studies of biomechanical movements.

1. The optical tracking technology and the equipment

Optical tracking is a sub-category of positional tracking. The purpose is to detect a body's rotations and translations to represent it in virtual reality. IR (InfraRed) cameras are used. Their principle consists in emitting IR light to make it reflect on a specific marker placed on the body whose movement wants to be studied. The reflection is then detected by the cameras's sensor [6]. With it, it is possible to calculate the marker's position in 2D, and if multiple cameras are used, the marker's location can be determined in space at every moment by 3D-reconstruction.

Markers may be of diverse types, they serve the same purpose: being detected by IR cameras. Their size influences the distance at which it is detectable, the bigger it is, the further the cameras can determine its location. But a little size is preferable for precise tracking. As we wanted to determine angles of inclinations, which requires precision, we opted for little markers.

During the experiment, we used two distinct kinds of markers: flats ones and spheres, in other words, volumes. Spheres are attached to a little round and flat support, this one being placed on the skin or any other surface we want to focus on. The main advantage of spheres is that they offer a bigger surface of reflection and provide thereby more information and make their detection easier. But they are also more difficult to place because making them stable is harder. And unstability is the last thing we want for it biases reflection, and thus, the exact representation of the movement.

All the equipment we used were from the brand OptiTrack. The cameras are the model V100 R2. The flat markers are Skin Tape Adhesive, reference MBA10MMS, and have a 10mm diameter. The spheres have a 9.5 mm diameter, of reference MKR095M3-10. They can be seen in figure 9 and 10.

The experiment had to be led on another part of the campus, where was present a dedicated laboratory equipped with the cameras.

2. The protocol and the data collection

As for the previous study, a protocol was written (see in annex 8).

Samila and I booked the laboratory once our inclinable support was ready (see figure 19 or below figure 10). Indeed, the protocol planned to study the alteration of amplitude for various angles of inclination: the same angles that those described later (see MISSION 3, p.26). This study for various angles had a precise purpose: to help us determine in the end what is the ideal position of use for the patients. Mr. Andrade joined us, and volunteered to be our subject. Markers were placed on him at the locations indicated in the protocol.

Figure 9 : Markers placed for the study without the device, and with the device

Data were collected, with and without the orthosis, for various angles of inclination, three times each.

Figure 10 : Acquisition of the wrist's amplitude with IR cameras

3. The data processing

Because of a technical problem that occurred sooner in the internship, Samila and I were unable to do the acquisitions. We had to wait until the very end, and I did not have time to look at the data. Thereby, I won't be in measure to provide

results. Nonetheless, the method is given and explained. This last is detailed using present, for it wasn't used.

As mentioned previously, the wrist's movement during flexion and extension is modelised by a circle arc. It is then assumed the movement can be described by a single coordinate z . We chose to take as radius the length between K and W (see annex 6, figure 29) and not L , because of the troubles we may have to make a sphere marker (which is necessary here because of the precision which is required) stick firmly to the handle of the orthosis.

The acquisition provides, for each marker, its coordinates over time. We export them to Excel. We focus on K (see protocol) and select its column of data. We display the highest and the lowest value(s): z_{max} and z_{min} . The figure below represents the travel of the marker.

Figure 11 : Modelisation of the movement and position of the marker K

We want to determine the amplitude, noted ρ in figure 11. We agree it is equal to $180 - \beta_1 - \beta_2$, with β_1 and β_2 the angles between M and vertical.

With trigonometry, we determine β_1 and β_2 :

$$\begin{cases} \cos(\beta_1) = \frac{z_{max}}{L} \Leftrightarrow \beta_1 = \arccos\left(\frac{z_{max}}{L}\right) \\ \cos(\beta_2) = \frac{z_{min}}{L} \Leftrightarrow \beta_2 = \arccos\left(\frac{z_{min}}{L}\right) \end{cases}$$

So,

$$\rho = 180 - \arccos\left(\frac{z_{max}}{L}\right) - \arccos\left(\frac{z_{min}}{L}\right)$$

The length R being known, we can determine the wrist's amplitude using the previous expression for every angle of acquisition and for every subject.

4. Results

We present the results in the following tables:

		Wrist's amplitude (degrees)
Without the orthosis	0°	
	18°	
	45°	
	90°	
With the orthosis	0°	
	18°	
	45°	
	90°	

Tableau 4: Wrist's amplitude in function of the orthosis and the positions of use

	Absolute difference	Relative difference
0°		
18°		
45°		
90°		

Table 5 : Table of results for the amplitudes

In table 4, we compare the results of table 3 by pairs. For example, the two cases colored in blue. As mentioned in the protocol, a relative difference inferior or equal to 10% between both is accepted, otherwise, a new axis will have to be bought or the structure of the device itself modified.

We keep in mind those results have been obtained on a healthy subject, whose wrist's amplitude is therefore superior to a parkinsonian's. Taking this into account, having a motion alteration close to 0% is not necessary, a low percentage is acceptable.

So, we end up with various cases we choose to treat as follows:

- If the relative difference is superior to 10%, the angle of use in question is not appropriate
- If the relative difference is between 5% and 10%, we consider the angle of use acceptable to perform the first tests
- If the relative difference is inferior to 5%, the angle of use is appropriate and as a higher probability to be accepted as the ideal angle of use

IV. Conclusion

I can't unfortunately draw a proper conclusion without having the results available. "Only" (if I dare to say) values are missing, all the upstream work being already done. Saying whether the amplitude offered by the orthosis is acceptable or not will have to wait a bit longer.

This study, as the ones that follows contributes to the determination of the ideal position of use, the position in which the patient will perform the movements playing a key role in his/her performances and in the comfort of use. It may be important of course to make the device as achieved as it can be, but in our current situation, as it is said previously, a partial amplitude (in our limits of acceptation) can be sufficient and acceptable for now, the time to lead the first tests on the patients.

III. The angle of the plan

As shown on figure 13, we placed ourselves in a cartesian mark, where was considered a plan described by the two-axes x and y. The plan is inclined with an angle α , which corresponds to the angle between the actuator and a flat surface of use, a table for instance.

A goniometer was used to measure the angle α :

Figure 13: Angle measurement between the actuator and the surface of use

This means the actuator is not in a parallel position compared to the surface of use.

More precisely, we wanted to study the forces for four different angles, called ϑ , with $\vartheta \in \{0^\circ; 162^\circ; 135^\circ; 90^\circ\}$. With this constant inclination of 18° , the angle α varies: $\alpha \in \{18^\circ; 0^\circ; -27^\circ; -72^\circ\}$.

IV. The mass of the motion part

The mass we considered is the mass the patients will have to put in movement by a mechanical action. This included, according to the annex 7, the parts 2, 3, 6, 7 and 8, without forgetting the weight of the hand.

The total mass of the motion part is equal to⁵ :

$$m_{motion} = m2 + m3 + m6 + m7 + m8 = 411,7g$$

The relative mass of a human hand corresponds to 0,61% of the total body mass for a man, and to 0,56% of a woman's one (Zatsiorsky-Seluyanov, "Contemporary Problems in Biomechanics", 1990) [6]. The average masses of the Brazilian population are respectively for men and women 73kg and 63 kg.

The orthosis, which is still a prototype, is devoted to be first used on patients from the « Associação Parkinson do Triângulo ». A census of the patients revealed an equal distribution between the genders (we selected 30 patients, 15 were male,

⁵ See in picture 30, page 56

15 were female), which allowed us to calculate a mean without weighting to determine m_{hand_mean} . This last was then equal to:

$$m_{hand} = \frac{m_{menhand} + m_{womenhand}}{2} = \frac{0,61 \cdot 73 + 0,56 \cdot 63}{2} = 399g, \text{ from which}$$

$$m_{tot} = m_{motion} + m_{hand} = 810,7g$$

From now on, m_{tot} is noted m .

V. The forces

We considered all the forces that apply on the mass, neglecting only friction due to the air. As shown of figure 12, weight, as well as the normal force and friction (mainly due to the contact between the central axis and the actuator). The acceleration noted a depends on the experimental conditions, and affects the product $m * a$, which is no other than the value of \vec{F}_{acc} .

VI. The parameters

Enabling everyone to use the orthosis was the cornerstone of the project. Various parameters had to be considered, for every patient is different from another.

Indeed, the time one needs to perform a successive flexion and extension, the amplitude the wrist enables to reach, the position of use which is the most comfortable. All these parameters differ because of the way one is affected by the disease.

Thereby, here are the parameters we chose to focus on:

- The angle of use: $\alpha \in \{18^\circ; 0^\circ; -27^\circ; -72^\circ\}$.
- The time to perform a flexion or an extension: $t \in \{0.5s; 1.0s; 1.5s\}$.
- The stroke length: $s \in \{17.5 \text{ cm}; 15 \text{ cm}; 12.5 \text{ cm}\}$.

Every single combinaison was studied. Flexions and extensions were studied independantly.

VII. Newton's second law: the mechanical approach

1. Overview of the problem

We had to make approximations to facilitate the problem. First, air friction was neglected. Secondly, the coefficient of friction due to the axis was, according to the dataheet of the motor, assumed equal to 0,2 [8].

The actuator is here to provide a force, in other words, to accelerate (or not) the mass. In every case, it must counter friction which is, by definition, opposed to the movement. But depending on the parameters, it can have to counter the

weight (or not) and to provide an acceleration (if the weight acting on the mass isn't sufficient to make it move).

It is well-known that theoretical calculations rarely stick perfectly to reality, for nothing is absolutely neglectable, and because as precise as our estimations can be (like the ones to determine m_{hand}), they remain estimations. Because it is the closest one to reality, or at least the one that fits the best our expectations, based on what we want from the patient, we considered a trapezoidal speed profile.

A complete movement could then be described as follows:

Figure 14 : Successive steps of a complete movement for a trapezoidal speed profile – LM2070-08011's dataheet, Faulhaber [8]

I recall that we aimed at helping patients to initiate the movement. I then only focused on the steps framed in red on the previous figure.

From the technical information of the actuator was extracted [9], the formula to calculate the acceleration corresponding to our speed profile:

$$a = 4,5 * \frac{s}{t^2} (\Delta)$$

2. Theoretical calculations

We wanted to determine the expression of all the forces. Newton's second law came into play and we obtained in the end, in the mark defined on figure 13:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{P} &= \begin{pmatrix} m * g * \sin(\alpha) \\ -m * g * \cos(\alpha) \end{pmatrix} \\ \vec{N} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -P_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ m * g * \cos(\alpha) \end{pmatrix} \\ \vec{f} &= \begin{pmatrix} \mu N \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu * m * g * \cos(\alpha) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Calculations are detailed in annex 8.

The last force was the one caused by the acceleration: F_{acc} . This last depends on the stroke length (the distance to travel) and the time we want the movement to last, both have been mentioned in the development.

To make easier the calculations to come, the expression (Δ) was used to obtain the following table:

Distance (cm)	Time (s)	Acceleration (m.s ⁻²)	Force _{acc} (N)
17,5	0,5	3,15	2,55
	1,0	0,79	0,64
	1,5	0,25	0,28
15,0	0,5	2,70	2,19
	1,0	0,68	0,55
	1,5	0,30	0,24
12,5	0,5	2,25	1,82
	1,0	0,56	0,45
	1,5	0,25	0,20

Table 6 : Force caused by the acceleration based on different parameters

In the same way, thanks to the expressions of the forces found previously we could calculate the apparent weight and the friction for the four angles of study, the apparent weight being the force a body exerts while resting on a surface. If gravity is not balanced by a normal force, weight and apparent weight are not equal. In daily life, no difference is made while we talk about weight. Calling the force "weight" would not have prevented the understanding of the problem, nor modified the results, but it is not as if it costed anything to mention it.

Angle _{surf-struct}	Angle _{surf-actuator}	Apparent Weight (N)	F _{friction} (N)
$\vartheta_1 = 0^\circ$	$\alpha_1 = 18^\circ$	$P_1 = 2,45$	$F_1 = 1,51$
$\vartheta_2 = 18^\circ$	$\alpha_2 = 0^\circ$	$P_2 = 0$	$F_2 = 1,59$
$\vartheta_3 = 45^\circ$	$\alpha_3 = -27^\circ$	$P_3 = 3,61$	$F_3 = 1,41$
$\vartheta_4 = 90^\circ$	$\alpha_4 = -72^\circ$	$P_4 = 7,56$	$F_4 = 0,49$

Table 7 : Apparent weight and friction based on the inclination angle

Here, we had at our disposal everything which was needed to pursue. Lots of calculations had to be made, only one is displayed below as an example, the others following the same method.

3. Example of calculation

Let's consider the first case: $\alpha = 18^\circ$, $t = 0,5s$, $s = 17,5cm$

May it be for flexion or extension, a is the same, and $a = 4,5 * \frac{s}{t^2} = 4,5 * \frac{17,5 * 10^{-2}}{0,5^2} = 3,15 m/s^2$.

Which implies that $m * a = F_{acc} = 0,8107 * 3,15 = 2,55 N$

Friction is equal to $f = \mu * m * g * \cos(\alpha) = 0,2 * 0,8107 * 9,81 * \cos(18) = 1,51 N$

The weight is equal to $P = m * g * \sin(\alpha) = 0,8107 * 9,81 * \sin(18) = 2,45 N$

During flexion, the weight comes along with the movement⁶ : it « helps ». It means the actuator doesn't have to counter it. During extension, it is the contrary, so we have:

$$\begin{cases} F_{flex} = F_{acc} - P + f = 1,61 N \\ F_{ext} = F_{acc} + P + f = 6,52 N \end{cases}$$

4. Results

As expected, the more the angle of use is important, the faster we want the movement to be performed and the distance travelled, the more the force the actuator needs to provide is important.

It occurred nonetheless cases where negative values were found. They informed us the mass could be put in movement « alone », under the weight's influence without the action of the motor. But to meet the specified expectations (see the parameters), the motor's action is here to slow down the movement. Otherwise, under the mass of the axis and of its own hand, if the hypothesis where one's wrist is weak, the movement could get « out of control », too fast, and cause pain.

Of course, the motor can't provide a negative force, the sign " - " only indicates the force opposes itself to the movement.

We only display here the results for the first angle, others are provided in annex 9.

$$\vartheta = 180^\circ / \alpha = 18^\circ$$

		Force (N)	
		Flexion	Extension
t=0,5s	s =17,5cm	1,61	6,52
	s=15cm	-0,30	4,60
	s=12,5cm	-0,66	4,24
t=1,0s	s=17,5cm	1,25	6 ,15
	s=15cm	-0,39	4,51
	s=12,5cm	-0,7	4,20
t=1,5s	s=17,5cm	0,88	5,78
	s=15cm	-0,49	4,41
	s=12,5cm	-0,74	4,16

Tableau 8 : Forces for a 18° angle

⁶ In this very case, because in others it may not always true

VIII. Conclusion

The motor we are using is the Faulhaber LM2070-080-11. Its maximum force is 9,2 N. Another one was at our disposal, but it could only provide a 3,2 N force. Thereby, we chose the first one.

It means except for the colored values in Table 12, annex 9, the one corresponding to a -72° angle values where the inclinaison is very demanding, the motor could fit all our expectations. At my arrival, two actuators had already been bought, and no other had been planned to be.

The results we had now were about to serve two major purposes. The first one: enabling an accurate programming of the micro-controller (which controls the actuator), making it adapt itself to lots of different situations. Secondly, knowing the orthosis must be seen as a recovering tool, it is going to enable the researchers, the physiotherapists or even the patients themselves, to plan training sessions based on the capacities of each and on what the objectives to reach are.

MISSION 3-BIS: The relative inertia of the device

I. Introduction

Thanks to our previous study about inertia, we knew what forces were required to initiate the movement according to various parameters. These forces are absolute, in other words they do not depend on the person who is using the orthosis.

What we wanted after this, was to get an additional tool of comprehension and assessment of the patient's performances: we wanted first to determine what was the relative force they needed to provide to do a movement (relative inertia) for various positions of use (1), and to quantify the amount of additional force the use of the orthosis was implying in terms of additional percentage of MVC (2).

More especially, we wanted to develop an experimental protocol and an operating method of data processing for further studies to come. Thereby, the results that will be presented do not matter a lot, and only a few will be said about them, for they were not the objective to reach.

The purpose of these data collection and processing methods that were developed was to have a better understanding of what the patients were going to be submitted to, to improve their future follow-up and make it as personal and as targeted as possible⁷.

Samila and I then led the experiment on Mr. Andrade only, who volunteered once again.

II. The idea

What we needed to determine was percentages, in other words ratios. More especially ratios of performances, which implied we had to see first what a subject was capable of in terms of maximal strength to carry out (1).

1. The Maximum Voluntary Contraction

MVC is the maximum force one can produce while performing an isometric exercise [10]. It is a technique that enables to assess a person's full muscular potential. It is usually determined by taking the mean of three efforts, (or best of them) performed in a single test session.

In our case, we wanted to determine the MVC of the muscles responsible for flexions and extensions of the wrist.

It exists lots of ways to determine the MVC, but we chose to proceed by employing electromyography.

⁷ When the orthosis will be ready

2. Electromyography

It is a detection technique which deals with electric potentials the muscles' cells generate when they are activated during an effort [11]. The goal is to record these potentials thanks to electrodes, to detect/determine various information, like abnormalities or an activation level (in our case).

We used here surface EMG, for the muscles that command flexion and extension of the wrist aren't located deep under the skin (see the muscles in question in annex 10)

An electrode is a device which enables the measure of a potential difference between two locations of a biological system. In our case, we used bipolar electrodes of the brand MediTrace. Unlike the monopolar configuration where a potential difference is measured between an active electrode and a reference by an instrumentation amplifier, two electrodes are used here (plus a reference), spaced of one or two centimeters from each-other. The potential difference measured is the one between the two electrodes. This technique proves to be better to increase the signal-to-noise ratio and thus, the quality of the EMG signal.

III. The determination of the relative forces

1. The data collection

When electromyography is being done, it is good to ensure nothing will disturb the measures, because it is a very sensitive technique. It appears the NIATS has a specific room dedicated to these kinds of experiments.

Figure 15 : Isolated room in which electromyographic acquisitions were led

As you can see, the walls are covered with a special foam which strongly attenuates perturbations coming from the outdoor, of mechanical nature (acoustic waves, radio waves, or else).

The protocol (in annex 10) gives all the necessary information about the experiment. Nonetheless, it is planned for numerous subjects. I recall the

measures were taken on one subject only, but the experiment described in the protocol remains the same.

Each signal was independently recorded in comparison with a reference placed on an osseous area (which is an electrically neutral tissue). Such an area can be (and was in our case), the styloid process of the ulna. The successions of flexion-extension were done with the orthosis, the MVCs without.

Figure 16: Subject about to carry out the experiment, for a regular and non-inclined movement, and for a MVC.

I warmly recommend the reader to read the protocol before pursuing.

2. The data processing

Mr. Andrade already had in mind precise expectations about the way he intended to process the data, using Matlab. "Only" the script had to be written. Its key-steps key steps are given in annex 11.

So, for each signal (MVCs and "normal ones"), we followed the steps described below:

1) Filtering of the signal

We applied a butterworth high-pass filter (function *butter*) of order 6 to obtain a flat response in the passband, with a cut-off frequency of 30 Hz, which corresponded to the offset due to the residual activity of the muscles. An order 4 could have been chosen as well, significant differences weren't observed. After the filter was synthesised we called the function *filtfilt* which filtered our signal without inducing any phase shift.

2) Estimation of its envelope

The envelope is basically what « surrounds » the signal. It is a curved obtained from its lower and the upper values. The envelope is easier to work with because it displays the signal's profile without all the quick fluctuations that often gives it its disorganised aspect.

We used the function *envelope*, by specifying the parameter *rms* (*root mean square*). This way we worked with positive values, all of them being representative of the contribution brought during the effort.

An illustration of what was obtained for the two first steps is given in annex 12.

3) Smoothing of the signal

The envelope we got was subject to tiny and brief fluctuations, making our next step (the detection of the peaks) inefficient. The smoothing (function *smooth*) made the aspect of the envelope clearer and the different peaks easier to locate.

4) Detection of the peaks

The peaks are the highest amplitudes reached by the envelope of the signal. They indicated us the moment where the effort was the most intense, and enabled us to quantify the effort in question. As we were only interested in comparing efforts in terms of maximal strength, not in getting the trend of the effort or else, we focused on the peaks, using the function *findPeaks* asking it only to display peaks above a certain abscissa, knowing 300 in our case, to avoid detecting non relevant peaks from the relaxation phase due to tiny contractions.

At this step I obtained this kind of figure:

Figure 17 : Detection of the peaks example, first flexion-extension succession, 0°, with the orthosis

We distinguish clearly the eight phases of contraction on the graphics, for flexion (graphic 1) and extension (graphic 2). As shown on the picture, the black stars and circles indicate the location of the peaks, which correspond to the higher voltage recorded by the electrodes, and thus, to the most intense phase of the contraction.

5) Returning of the peaks' mean value.

We calculated the mean of the peaks's value. This way, we made sure our estimation was representative of the effort performed by the subject. This is these means that enabled us to conclude, because they were the numeric feedback of our acquisitions.

6) Calculation of the ratios

This step amounts to the conclusion of the processing.

For (1), μ_{MVC_flex} and μ_{MVC_ext} were used as reference to determine the percentage of force required to move the wrist while equipped or not with the orthosis and were therefore the denominators of our ratios.

For (2), concerning the comparison between the use with and without the orthosis, we did absolute comparisons. We subtracted the percentage of MVC a flexion (respectively an extension) required in a given position, with the orthosis, to the percentage of MVC a flexion (respectively an extension) required in the same position, without the orthosis. In the end, this is an absolute difference that we made.

3. Results

We obtained $\mu_{MVC_flex} = 629.5 \mu V$ and $\mu_{MVC_ext} = 244.4 \mu V$. So far, the only thing it indicates is that flexors are more powerful than extensors. Nothing new, nor relevant for us. We wanted to represent our results on graphics. The one below presents the results of objective (1):

Figure 18 : Percentage of MVC required to do a movement in various positions, with and without the orthosis

"O" indicates measures were performed with the orthosis, "NO" (No orthosis) indicates the contrary.

Statistically speaking, these results are not relevant because only one subject was submitted to the experiment. To give an example of interpretation, figure 18 indicates that at 0°, when the subject was equipped with the orthosis, flexors of his forearm needed to provide more than 30% of their full potential to enable the user to flex his wrist.

From these results, we can determine (2). To quantify the difference of force in terms of percentage of MVC, we had the idea to introduce an ergonomic index. This last reflects to what extent the orthosis impacts the movement in terms of difference of MVC percentage requirement, between a use with and without the orthosis, for flexions and extensions dealt separately. The percentage the EI taken into account are those presented in the previous figure. To make things clearer, the closer it is to 1, the easier it is to perform a movement with the orthosis. The ergonomic index (EI) is defined as follows:

$$EI = 1 - \frac{\%MVC_{with\ orthosis}}{\%MVC_{without\ orthosis}}$$

From which:

Figure 19 : Ergonomic index comparison

What figure 19 shows is that the higher the angle of inclination is, the easier it is to perform extension. The contrary goes for flexion which becomes harder. The explanation arises from the impact of the weight of the motion part of the orthosis, which helps the extensors and make the task of the flexors more difficult as the angle of inclination increases. Once again, discussing the values themselves may not be of much statistical interest, for they were obtained from a single subject. What is important is to notice the trend, which is conform to our expectations and to the theoretical results (see annex 9).

IV. Conclusion

The main objective was to develop a new tool of assessment for patients, to get used to acquire, process, and manipulate new datas. So far, we reached our objective. Electromyographic signals were of decent quality, and the script written on Matlab enabled an efficient processing via the identification and the extraction of the most relevant data. Introducing the ergonomic index turned out to be a clever idea, because of its ability not only to capture information about ergonomics, but also its ability to tell us more about the way the muscles are solicited. Thanks to this study, the orthosis will be able to give access to another variable of assessment: the relative inertia, subjective, and thereby more personal.

MISSION 4: The ideal position of use

I. Introduction

The last variable which was identified as describing and impacting the orthosis's behavior was the position of the forearm during the acquisition. At first sight, a flat position of use seemed adopted naturally by the different users, leading us not to consider any other angle of positioning. But this, was until Mr. Andrade felt good sensations while doing movements, with his forearm making a 90° angle with the table before him. From this point, we started considering various positions of use, and I then included them in our protocols, with the objective to determine, which one one them was the most comfortable and which one gave the best results.

II. A resultant of other variables

Considering the stability issue as solved, we identified the amplitude (i) and the relative inertia (ii) as the two main variables the ideal position depended of, for they were the only one left to provide experimental results.

As mentioned in the introduction, inclination had to be included in our protocols. We had the area of the support shown on figure 21 by the yellow arrow modified so that it can rotate. The height is also adjustable, thanks to a screw shown by the blue arrow.

Figure 20 : Support with adjustable inclination and height

The objective is to consider both (i) and (ii) to identify interesting associations of parameters, knowing an angle of use with a low alteration of motion and an

acceptable strength requirement for the patients. Of course, the notion of "acceptable strength" is fuzzy and subjective, but it is nonetheless the way to go to ensure them the best follow-up. Which brings me to say the ideal position of use may not be absolute, but variable from an individual to another.

III. Conclusion

The ideal position of use may remain unknown, all the tools are available to determine it. Results of further studies, like the ones which will be focused on patients will come to join the ranks of the data collected so far.

This variable, which was far from being considered in the beginning may prove to be essential to improve the comfort of patients during acquisitions, as well as the recovering process.

FINAL MISSION: The paper

I. Introduction

Since my professor started his research on the orthotic device, he didn't publish any article about it. It was to this day still unknown to the scientific community. Though the device was still a prototype, seeing the improvements we had succeeding in doing so far, the results we were starting to gather with our ideas and experiments, and the collaborations which were emerging here and there, especially with the Royal Society, Mr. Andrade decided in November time had come to move on to the next stage and to present his work through a paper. At this occasion, we were joined by Mr. Okereke, a British professor specialized in the study of finite elements, so that he can learn more about the project and lay the groundwork of his future contribution to the study, in particular in the modelisation of the orthosis.

II. The Congress

The good opportunity presented itself with the holding of the World Congress on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering. Supervised by the IUPESM, the International Union for Physical and Engineering Science in Medical, it is an event that takes place every three years in a different country. The next one is this year, next June in Prague [12].

During the congress are scheduled conferences of speakers of all nationalities, special sessions about new and innovative areas in biomedical, scientific visits of key places of research and innovation in Czech Republic.

An abstract of the paper⁸ we intended to present had to be submitted first before November 15th, so we carried out. This last was accepted, leaving us some time to pursue our research before the deadline fixed on January 31st. The abstract is enclosed in annex 13.

III. The content of the paper

In addition to a description of the motive of the research establishing the link between Parkinson's disease and our work, at which was added a mechanical description of the orthosis, the paper covered in fact the content of my internship, knowing the presentation of the studied variables, the reason why we were focusing on them, the proposed improvements and the results of their assessments. So, the title of the paper was chosen accordingly: " Ergonomic assessment of an active orthosis for the rehabilitation of flexion and extension of wrist". We were four to contribute to the writing: Mr. Andrade, Samila, Mr. Okereke and myself, each of us having a defined part of the paper to write, mine being the one dealing with the results.

⁸ The paper in question was a conference paper, so it had to be quite short, not to exceed six pages in our case, and hadn't necessarily have to deal with a finished work.

Conclusions and perspectives

Although the first month of my internship was long and not really productive due to the absence of my professor and the fact I had to integrate myself in a project already launched, spent the time to find the role I had to play and the contribution I was going to bring, the rest of internship went well. My ideas were better focused, and my time better spent.

As you will have understood, my work consisted in the identification, in proposals of improvements and in assessments of the orthosis' key variables in order to make it a device for the parkinsonians' rehabilitation as efficient and as reliable as possible. Everything may not have been finished, because of technical problems or simply because of time (see MISSION 2 and thus MISSION 4), but what was done was done well, for I always seek to be as rigorous as I could. I am very glad my work and efforts during these four months and a half-satisfied Mr. Andrade and Samila.

The experiments we led may only have been pilot ones, thanks to our combined efforts, the understanding of the orthosis, of its current state with its flaws and qualities, and of the upcoming challenges to come, improved. We now have at our disposal new data to consider for the future studies to come and are now able to make a better use of the device.

I think Mr. Okereke and I gave a new impetus to the project, by bringing a new regard, new results, by making Mr. Andrade reconsider the potential of the tool he had in his hands and that he spent years to design, whose use could be extended in the future to people involved in accidents, burns, or strokes.

After our departure, the objective is to maintain this dynamic. The ideal position of use still remains undetermined, but my contribution should lead to its determination. A new material will soon be considered to replace the current one (aluminium). Memory form plastic is already envisaged, to ensure solidity and to make the device easily adaptable to everyone in terms of dimension.

During this experience, I achieved something I wanted to do for long, getting familiar with the world of Research, a mix of challenging work, team spirit, collaboration, patience, frustration and satisfaction. I had the chance, if I dare to say, to experience all of them, even if at times there are some I regretted to find on my road.

I am glad I have been able to test my skills, may they be technical or human, as well as to discover new things. I manipulated for the first-time inertial sensors, IR cameras and made use of electromyography. The writing of the paper was a first for me, very enriching, and gave a good overview of what had been achieved so far. It constituted another objective to reach and a real source of motivation for me.

Also, I learned more about Parkinson's disease. In people's mind, it is often only associated to tremors, and nothing more. Several works are currently led based on this statement, but patients have a lot more to deal with in their daily life. Mr. Andrade understood it, and inspired his research from the fact that

according to testimonies collected with the patients themselves, muscular stiffness is as disabling, if not more.

I had the opportunity to meet some of those patients at the Parkinson Association, undergoing various stages of advancement of the disease, to discuss a bit with them, and to become aware of how impacting the pathology is, which remains to this day, one of the most feared in the world.

I planned to remain in contact with Adriano (and the members of the NIATS who all have been very nice to me), who already proposed me to keep me informed of the events to come, and to maybe join him to the World Congress in Prague.

I can't finish properly without saying this stay in Brazil was more than enriching. There, I discovered a new culture, more focused on human relations. People made my integration as easy and as enjoyable as one can wish. The least I could do was to engage myself in the learning of portuguese that I am glad to speak quite well now. The people I met are awesome, and I wish them all the best.

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Annexes

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Annex 1: Presentation of Tinkercad

Tinkercad is an online 3D modeling platform edited by Autodesk. Its use is voluntarily made very easy to enable the largest number of people to get familiar with it. Its operating principle is based on the modification and the combination of simple geometric pieces (cube, cylinder, etc.) the user places on a 2D-plan. Precision is of the order of tenth of a millimeter. Files can be imported on the platform to be modified, and others can be exported. Two formats are proposed: obj and stl. What makes the platform interesting in my case is the fact it is mostly dedicated to 3D-printing. It is also good to know the platform proposes a service of impression and delivery.

Annex 2: Protocol MISSION 1

Assessment of the answer brought by the support in terms of stability

Introduction

It was previously noticed the instability of the device during its use, causing discomfort for the patient, and making measures unreliable knowing we want to collect data to assess the efficiency (or inefficiency) of the orthosis. Indeed, once placed on the forearm, if the patient performs movements, the device oscillates from right to left: it is no longer in the axis of the flexion and extension of the wrist.

Problem

How to counter the problem of stability to meet our needs without having to alter the structure of the orthosis?

Hypothesis

A support of the shape of the forearm placed under the orthosis provides stability once attached to it.

Study method

Situation

An inertial measurement unit is placed on the structure of the device (worn by the subject), at the base of the support of the actuator, perpendicular to it (this condition is only to save space). The arm is positioned on a flat surface.

Tools

- The orthosis
- The support
- An inertial measurement unit (accelerometer, gyroscopes) and magnetometers
- Tremsen Software (acquisition and visualisation of the variations detected)
- Tremsen Hardware (amplification of the variations)
- Matlab software (data processing)

Figure 21 : Experimental material

Collect and processing

We only focus here on the accelerometer. We launch the acquisition on Tremsen and the subject performs successive flexions and extensions during a period of 20 seconds, this time being enough to collect enough of them to make them representative. This operation is done five times using the orthosis, five times without. Data are then exported to Matlab where a script processes them. The different axes are studied to determine where occur the strongest variation of acceleration.

Analyse of the results

The objective being to determine the (lateral) displacement of the orthosis, the signals are integrated twice.

For each signal of displacement, the mean and the standard deviation are calculated. Ten means and ten standards deviations are then obtained (five of each for flexions, respectively extensions)

Some additional steps lead to the estimation of a range of displacement, one describing the behaviour of the orthosis with support, the other without. These two intervals are compared.

Conclusion

We do not set any range of acceptance. We only expect the relative difference to be high enough so that the improvement can be real. If it is, the support will have proved to be efficient and will be included and the further experiments to ensure decent quality measures. If not, a new solution will have to be considered.

Annex 3: Presentation of Matlab

Matlab (for Matrix laboratory) is a numerical computing environment owned by the MathWorks Inc., originally dedicated to matrix manipulation, hence the name which is also given to the programming language used by the software, to implement algorithms, interfaces, to plot functions and to visualise data. A compiler is available for this purpose. Matlab enables the user to program in other languages as well, like in C, C++, Java or Python.

Matlab is a powerful environment, very complete, for it offers hundreds of mathematical functions already implemented, gathered in libraries (ToolBoxes) directly accessible from the command line. The software aims at facilitating data processing and meets a remarkable success among scientists, especially those dealing with signal and image processing. A tool of modelisation, Simulink, is also proposed by the software. This last is compatible with Windows, Mac and Linux.

Annex 4: M-scripts key steps to assess stability

```
1 %KEY STEP 1: Removal of the linear trend
2
3 X_with      = AlX;
4 X_without   = AlX1;
5
6 %removal of the linear trend
7
8 |   %polyfit finds coefficient of a polynomial that fits the best the data
9 p_with      = polyfit(Time,X_with,1); %order 1 -> P(X) = aX -> linear
10 p_without   = polyfit(Time,X_without,1);
11 |   %polyval returns the value of polyfit's polynomial
12 y_with      = polyval(p_with,Time);
13 y_without   = polyval(p_without,Time);
14
15 |   %linear trending of the value, subtraction of the values
16 |   %of the fitting polynomial to the signal
17 lin_detrend_with = X_with - y_with;
18 lin_detrend_without = X_without - y_without;
19
20 %KEY STEP 2: Removal of the nonlinear trend -> polynomial detrending
21
22 %Removal of trend with support
23 [p,s,mu] = polyfit(Time,lin_detrend_with,order);
24 fy = polyval(p,Time,[],mu);
25 pol_detrend_with = lin_detrend_with - fy;
26
27 clear fy p s mu
28
29 %Removal of trend without support
30 [p,s,mu] = polyfit(Time,lin_detrend_without,order);
31 fy = polyval(p,Time,[],mu);
32 pol_detrend_without = lin_detrend_without - fy;
```

Figure 22 : Capture of the code, part 1

```
34 %KEY STEP 3: Displacement analysis
35
36 order=6; %order of the polynomial, function polyfit
37
38
39 |   % cumtrapz integrate the input data
40 |   % intergration of acceleration to get velocity
41 V_with      = cumtrapz(Time,pol_detrend_with)*1e3;
42 V_without   = cumtrapz(Time,pol_detrend_without)*1e3;
43
44 |   % intergration of velocity to get vdisplacement
45 D_with      = cumtrapz(Time, V_with);
46 D_without   = cumtrapz(Time,V_without);
47
48 |   % mean of the displacement
49 m_with      = mean(D_with);
50 m_without   = mean(D_without);
51
52 |   % constant curves whose values are their respective means
53 |   % to observe the position of the displacement around them
54 line_m_with = ones(length(Time),1)*m_with;
55 line_m_without = ones(length(Time),1)*m_without;
56
57 |   % standard deviation of the displacement
58 error_with  = std(D_with);
59 error_without = std(D_without);
```

Figure 23: Capture of the code, part 2

Annex 5: Theoretical calculation to determine the ideal length of the axis

We place ourselves in the situation the amplitude is a healthy subject's one. We use trigonometry. As we consider lengths, we manipulate radians.

During flexion the axis blocks because of the length a_2 .

a_2 must then at least be $\frac{|\alpha_{flex}| * \pi * j}{180}$ tall, in other words: $a_{2required} \geq 11.2 \text{ cm}$

During extension, the axis blocks because of the length a_1 .

a_1 must then at least be $\frac{|\alpha_{ext}| * \pi * j}{180}$ tall, in other words: $a_{1required} \geq 12.7 \text{ cm}$

It is important to keep in mind that all length lost on one side of the actuator during movement is regained on the other, the length of the axis being constant.

Therefore, the required size of the axis is:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{required} &= b + \max \{ a_{1required}, a_{2required} \} \\ &= 4.8 + a_{1required} \\ &= 17.5 \text{ cm} \end{aligned}$$

Knowing the current value of our axis was 12.3 cm, it had to be at least increased of: $17.5 - 12.3 = 5.2 \text{ cm}$.

Annex 6: Protocol MISSION 2

Assessment of the wrist's amplitude alteration by the orthosis

Introduction

The orthosis we are working on was already subject to problems concerning amplitude. Its purpose is to be a « training tool » for patients, based on healthy standards. In other words, to claim we are developing a recovering tool, it must enable a patient suffering from a loss of amplitude to get it back entirely (in the ideal scenario of course, or at least to get back enough not to be bothered again in daily life tasks). The further they can go the better. A second motive leads us to assess the wrist's amplitude alteration: the cost a new-design or new axis would generate. With the replacement of the former axis with a longer one, amplitude was increased significantly, but is it enough?

Problem

Is the current amplitude one can reach with the device sufficient? Is it close enough to a normal one?

Hypothesis

The orthosis doesn't alter the maximum amplitude.

Study method

Tools

- Orthosis (support included, because it proved to be efficient, from now on it is part of the device)
- An inclinable support
- A software dedicated to motion capture (being in development, but nonetheless reliable, its name as well as any other specification about it are unknown because not communicated by the developer)
- Cameras Optitrack-V100 R2
- Markers Skin Tape Adhesive, Optitrack - MBA10MMS
- Excel

Situation

We want to compare the wrist's amplitude with and without the orthosis. Being of the same colour as the markers we are going to use, the orthosis is covered with black tape so that the markers are distinguished easily by the cameras to make the acquisitions possible and operable. The subject is then equipped with the device with no additional specification.

A subject carries out and performs 20 flexions and 20 extensions. We have at our disposal 10 cameras, placed in a way that avoids blind angles.

The software is calibrated considering the settings of the cameras and the parameters of the acquisition (time, near-static, small area of study). Unfortunately, no more can be said here.

The most important markers, or at least the most relevant, are those placed on the hand, especially K (see in figure 29 below), placed behind the knuckle of the middle finger, for he is the one which is going to provide us key information to determine the amplitude we are looking forward to determining. Others are only here to give « structure » to the acquisition, and even if they are not of much use here, they are nonetheless considered for any future study that could cover the modelisation of the movement. On the skin, spheres are used because they offer a larger surface of reflection, so they make the detection more precise, and skin areas are more subject to movement. The exception remains A, but the low size of the surface the axis offers makes the use of a sphere difficult, therefore a flat marker was chosen.

R, which is no other than the radius of the circle we assume the wrist draws, is the distance KW, and will be known precisely after recording, after the software will have spotted K and W.

Figure 24 : Placement of the markers

Collect

The subject is placed in the middle of the area surrounded by the cameras. He/She lays the forearm on the inclinable support, (set first to 0°), to ensure stability and to prevent him/her from keeping the arm extended during the whole acquisition.

For each subject, for each angle of use $\beta = \{0^\circ; 18^\circ; 45^\circ; 90^\circ\}$ ⁹, three acquisitions are made with the orthosis, and three without. 18° corresponds to the inclination of the actuator placed on top of the orthosis, so it is an interesting case to study.

No reference is necessary here. Indeed, we aim at determining an amplitude, in other words, a variable determined from an absolute difference between two measures. No matter the starting position of the wrist, it won't affect its flexion and its extension.

We launch the acquisition on the software and the subject performs the movements according to what has been mentioned.

The software registers the 3D-coordinates of the markers in different formats: txt, xlsx and c3d¹⁰. This way, data can be exported to R, Matlab, Excel or any other software able to read one of the three formats mentioned previously.

Results analysis

Based on the data we obtain, we can extract all the coordinates registered of the movement during time for each marker. As mentioned earlier we focus on the marker K. We modelise its movement as a circle arc, whose rotation axis in the wrist itself, whose radius R (see figure 14 or in figure 29) is known and whose angle ρ is the data we seek.

The movement moves along the z-axis, we extract with Excel the highest and lowest positions reached by K: z_{\max} and z_{\min} . From here, trigonometry enables us to determine the amplitude.

We then compare the results by pairs, with and without the orthosis for a specific angle of use.

According to our hypothesis, we want to obtain the same results. If not, a relative difference inferior or equal to 10% is accepted.

Conclusion

If the results are the same, the orthosis will have proved it doesn't alter the movement's amplitude, and that it can pretend to be a device that does not restrict patients's performances.

If not, a new axis will have to be bought or a new design of the orthosis will have to be considered. Both options generating additional costs.

⁹ We recall we do not know what is the best position of use yet, therefore all cases are studied.

¹⁰ Coordinate 3D is a format that holds the parameters and their data altogether. It is especially designed to contain 3D coordinates. It aims at minimizing storage requirements and at optimizing the speed and efficiency of access to data.

Annex 7: Weight of the orthosis

Figure 25 : Different pieces of the orthosis

NUMBER OF THE PIECE	DESCRIPTION OF THE PIECE	MASS (g)
1	Actuator	139.7
2	Central axis	143.8
3	Lateral axis (*2)	154.6
4	Axis and actuator support	219.6
5	Main structure (forearm)	135.4
6	Main structure (hand)	98.2
7	Stroke end screw	1.6
8	Screws that fix the spherical joint terminals (attach the structure of the hand to the structure of the forearm)	6.3
9	Screws that secure the actuator bracket and side shafts to the forearm structure.	7.2
10	Screw that secures the actuator to the structure of the support	1.2
11	Screw that secures the central axis to the structure of the parallel axes	1.2
12	Complete structure	908.8

Table 9 : Weight of the parts displayed in figure 30

Annex 8: Details of the mechanical theoretical calculations

We apply Newton's second law and all the expressions arises from it. If we keep the figure 14 in mind, we have:

$$\sum F = m * a = F_{acc} = F_{act} - P - f - N$$

from which we isolate F_{act} :

$$F_{act} = F_{acc} + P + f + N$$

Let's pay attention, this expression is not a vectorial expression. Depending on the angle α for example, P won't oppose itself to the movement and won't have to be countered by the actuator.

We now need to express each force with its components, to obtain vectorial equalities. The key is to express the weight. For this, we represent the problem as it is shown on the figure below:

Figure 26 : Components of the weight

We can determine P_x and P_y quite easily, by using trigonometry and from the previous figure we deduce:

$$\begin{cases} \sin(\alpha) = \frac{P_x}{m * g} \Leftrightarrow P_x = m * g * \sin(\alpha) \\ \cos(\alpha) = \frac{P_y}{m * g} \Leftrightarrow P_y = m * g * \cos(\alpha) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In our mark,

$$\vec{P}_y = -P_y \vec{y}$$

So,

$$\vec{P} = \begin{pmatrix} m * g * \sin(\alpha) \\ -m * g * \cos(\alpha) \end{pmatrix}$$

We also know that f is expressed on the x axis while N is only directed on the y one.

By definition, f is the result of the product of the coefficient of friction of the mass on the surface, noted μ and the apparent weight: the force a surface exerts on a body, which is here no other than the normal force N .

We write:

$$\vec{f} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu * N \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

And

$$\vec{N} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ N \end{pmatrix}$$

Moreover, the acceleration is only directed on the x axis, it means $a_y = 0$.
With all of this, we come back to the expression (1) and write:

$$\begin{cases} \vec{F}_x = \vec{P}_x + \vec{f} + \vec{F}_{acc} \\ \vec{F}_y = 0 = \vec{P}_y + \vec{N} \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \vec{F}_x = \vec{P}_x + \vec{f} + \vec{F}_{acc} \\ \vec{N} = -\vec{P}_y \end{cases}$$

We deduce that

$$\vec{N} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -P_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ m * g * \cos(\alpha) \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{f} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu N \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu * m * g * \cos(\alpha) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Annex 9: Other results of MISSION 2

$$\vartheta = 162^\circ / \alpha = 0^\circ$$

		Force (N)	
		Flexion	Extension
t=0.5s	s=17.5cm	4.14	4.14
	s=15cm	2.13	2.13
	s=12.5cm	1.87	1.87
t=1.0s	s=17,5cm	3.78	3.78
	s=15cm	2.14	2.14
	s=12.5cm	1.83	1.83
t=1.5s	s=17.5cm	3.41	3.41
	s=15cm	2.04	2.04
	s=12.5cm	1.79	1.79

Table 10 : Forces for a 0° angle

We notice here the nature of the movement has no effect on the value of the force. Indeed, even if the patient's arm is inclined, the actuator perceives an angle of 0° . The forces to flex or extend the wrist are then equal.

$$\vartheta = 135^\circ / \alpha = -27^\circ$$

		Force (N)	
		Flexion	Extension
t=0.5s	s=17.5cm	7.57	0.35
	s=15cm	5.66	-1.56
	s=12.5cm	5.30	-1.92
t=1.0s	s=17.5cm	7.21	-0.01
	s=15cm	5.57	-1.65
	s=12.5cm	5.26	-1.96
t=1.5s	s=17.5cm	6.84	-0.38
	s=15cm	5.47	-1.75
	s=12.5cm	5.22	-2.00

Table 11 : Forces for a -27° angle

$$\vartheta = 90^\circ / \alpha = -72^\circ$$

		Force (N)	
		Flexion	Extension
t=0.5s	s=17.5cm	10,60	-4.52
	s=15cm	8,69	-6.43
	s=12.5cm	8,33	-6.79
t=1.0s	s=17.5cm	10,24	-4.88
	s=15cm	8,60	-6.52
	s=12.5cm	8,29	-6.83
t=1.5s	s=17.5cm	9,87	-5.25
	s=15cm	8,50	-6.62
	s=12.5cm	8,25	-6.87

Table 12 : Forces for a $\alpha = -72^\circ$ angle

Annex 10: Protocol MISSION 3

Determination of the relative force one needs to perform the movement with the orthosis

Introduction

We now know what force each movement requires, based on various parameters, thanks to the theoric mechanical approach we already operated, see MISSION 3. These forces are absolute, they are the same for everyone.

In order to have at our disposal a new tool of comprehension and of assessment of patient's performances, we want two more things:

(1) To determine what is now the relative force patients need to provide to do a mouvement, for various positions of use. The answer will come by comparing a subject's Maximal Voluntary Contraction (MVC) to a "normal movement" he or she performs with the orthosis.

(2) We still want to assess the difference between a movement with and a movement without the device. So, for each subject, and for each position of use, the signal's amplitudes will be compared to the MVC (see 1) and then the percentages we will have obtained will be compared together, to quantify on every subject the impact of the device in terms of force requirement. As a result of 2, we will know what additional percentage of MVC the use of the orhosis requires, if it requires more of course.

Problem

1. What relative force moving the orthosis requires?
2. What additional percentage of the MVC the use of the orthosis requires compared to a movement performed without it?

Hypothesis

None.

Study method

Tools

- Bipolar electrodes (brand Meditrace)
- The software INTAN (configuration, visualisation, amplifying, registration and export of the acquisitions)
- Matlab (signal processing)

Situation

A group of subjects constitutes the group of reference. For each one of them, we place electrodes on the muscles responsible for flexion and extension after having sanitised the skin with alcohol.

The muscles responsible for flexion are:

- The flexor carpi radialis muscle
- The palmaris longus muscle
- The flexor carpi ulnaris muscle

The muscles responsible for extension are:

- The extensor carpi radialis muscle
- The extensor carpi radialis brevis muscle
- The extensor carpi ulnaris muscle

The illustration below shows the placement of the electrodes:

Being very close, we only put two electrodes for three muscles, without forgetting a reference, located on the free limb, on the process estiloide of the ulna, chosen for its osseus nature. The subject is then equipped with the orthosis.

Collect

First, we collect the subject's MVC for flexion, and for extension. For this, for 6 seconds, the subject is asked to perform a flexion (or an extension) as hard as he/she can while someone is voluntarily applying a pressure on his/her hand to block the movement. The applied pressure must be sufficient so that it prevents the wrist from moving. The operation is repeated three times, with a two-minute rest between each. The mean is then calculated between the three acquisitions.

After this, for four different angles $\in \{0^\circ; 18^\circ; 45^\circ; 90^\circ\}$, the subject performs eight complete movements without the orthosis during which flexions and extensions are picked up by their dedicated electrodes.

To finish, the subject does the same, with the orthosis this time.

Measures are done in a specific room, isolated from outside perturbation thanks to foam placed on its wall.

Result analysis

Data are exported to Matlab to be processed. The incoming signals are raw. For the "normal signals" (those composed of a succession of flexions and extensions), flexions and extensions are processed separately, in other words we get two signals from one. Indeed, even when one is flexing the wrist, the extensors aren't resting at 100%. The contrary is true as well. Each signal is filtered and has its envelope extracted. There, we locate the peaks of the signal, extract their value, to calculate the mean value of the signal's amplitude. The results are given in μV .

A mean MVC is calculated for flexion and for extension based on the three MVC acquisitions performed for each, we call them respectively called $\mu_{\text{MVC_flex}}$ and $\mu_{\text{MVC_ext}}$.

Means amplitudes are calculated as well for all the flexions and for all the extensions of "normal signals", with and without the orthosis. All of them are compared to the appropriate MVC in a first time, (objective 1), indeed we only compare flexions to flexions and extensions to extensions.

Then, the previous results are compared together to study the impact of the device concerning the relative force which must be provided in addition to do the movements while the orthosis is used (objective 2).

The results will be gathered in a table.

Conclusion

We have nothing to comment here, for we have nothing to prove or to assess. We only aim at determining mean values, standards, based on healthy subjects, without seeking to give an interpretation. Comments will come when this process will be done on patients.

Annex 11: M-scripts key steps of the EMG signals data processing

```
1 %KEY-STEP 1 : Filtering
2 n=6; %order of the filter
3 fs=1000; %sampling frequency, Hz
4 Wn=30/(fs/2); %cutoff frequency, Hz, with 1 Hz = 2π rad/s = 6.2831853 rad/s
5 type='high'; %type of the filter
6
7 [b,a]=butter(n,Wn,type); %creation of the filter
8 flex_filt=filtfilt(b,a,flexion); %filtering of flexion
9 ext_filt=filtfilt(b,a,extension); %filtering of extension
10
11 %KEY-STEP 2: Smoothing the extracted envelope
12 Wl=200;
13 flex_env = envelope (flex_filt, Wl, 'rms');
14 ext_env = envelope (ext_filt, Wl, 'rms');
15 % returns the RMS envelope (this is why the envelope is >0)
16 % of the signal over a sliding window of Wl samples.
17
18 flex_smooth=smooth(flex_env,100); %smoothes the envelope to erase all the tiny fluctuations
19 ext_smooth=smooth(ext_env,100);
20
21 %KEY-STEP 3: Localisation of the peaks
22 [values_peaks_flex_env,loc_peaks_flex_env]=findpeaks(flex_smooth,'MinPeakProminence',th_value);
23 [values_peaks_ext_env,loc_peaks_ext_env]=findpeaks(ext_smooth,'MinPeakProminence',th_value);
24 %locates the peaks of the envelope
25 %for ordinates superior to 300 to avoid considering
26 %the multitude of tiny peaks due to muscular tiny contractions
27
28 %KEY-STEP 4: Calculation of the means of the peaks
29 mean_flex_env = mean(values_peaks_flex_env);
30 mean_ext_env = mean(values_peaks_ext_env);
31 std_flex_env = std(values_peaks_flex_env);
32 std_ext_env = std(values_peaks_ext_env);
```

Figure 27 : Capture of the code

Annex 12: Results of the steps 1 and 2 of the data processing

Figure 28: Step 1, Filtering of the first flexion-extension succession, 0°, with the orthosis

Figure 29: Step 2, Envelope of the first flexion-extension succession, 0°, with the orthosis

Annex 13: Abstract of the paper

Title: Ergonomic assessment of an active orthosis for the rehabilitation of flexion and extension of wrist

Muscular stiffness and limb rigidity are two main consequences of Parkinson's disease. These motor symptoms may be present in distinct parts of the body, influencing over the execution of functional tasks, those executed by hands. In order to aid people suffering from these motor conditions, we developed an active wrist orthosis whose purpose is to enable increase in the angular amplitude of the flexion and extension of the wrist joint. We identified five relevant ergonomic variables that should be taken into account for using the orthosis in the clinical practice: (i) the mass of the device; (ii) the relative position of the arm while wearing the device; (iii) the influence of the orthosis on the natural flexion and extension of movements of the wrist; (iv) the stability of the orthosis on the arm; (v) the impact of inertia on the initiation of movements. These variables were identified based on the observation of movements while users executed the flexion and extension of the wrist with and without the device. In this research we present a description of the developed orthosis together with the evaluation of ergonomic variables that may impact on its practical use. A set of inertial sensors and infrared cameras was used for data collection, in order to objectively assess the variables. Based on this evaluation it is possible to suggest modifications in the current design of the orthosis so that it can be improved.

ERGONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF AN ACTIVE ORTHOSIS FOR PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS

Summary

As the world population grows older, Parkinson's disease (PD) affects more and more people. Targeting the nervous system, it mainly shows itself by tremors. Although these last remain widely disabling to execute daily tasks, patients do have to face other symptoms, like muscular rigidity which decreases liberty of movement. The disease biological's causes remain poorly understood, therefore other approaches must be considered to improve patients living condition.

This report describes my role within a laboratory currently developing an active orthosis whose shape matches the forearm of its user for rehabilitation of the users' wrist's range of motion that Parkinson's disease affects particularly. The purpose was to make the orthosis an operable and comfortable tool, which hereafter will be described as ergonomic. For this, key ergonomic variables were investigated, in particular stability, relative inertia (specific to each user) and the motion amplitude alteration, of an already existing prototype. These were identified as describing and governing the behaviour of the device. This pilot study was based initially on healthy subjects, and the understanding generated has contributed to expand our knowledge of the device. Methods of data collections and analysis were implemented and an assessment of the proposed improvements were undertaken using an user-generated MATLAB scripts, accelerometers, infra-red cameras, and electromyography.

To enhance the stability of the device, a 3D-printed polymeric support was designed and used to achievement an improvement of 77%. The minimum muscle strength (motion inertia) was determined objectively by devising a method based on the comparison of Maximum Voluntary Contraction with and without the user wearing the orthosis. A MATLAB routine was developed to analyse the data and determine successfully the motion inertia. Results concerning the motion amplitude alteration are awaited soon. Consequently, the research team is now equipped to explore other additional applications especially for patients who are involved in accidents, first-degree burns, or some partial strokes. Further large-scale studies on actual PD patients will now be undertaken based on the experimental protocols developed in this study. The patients will have to be offered personalised follow-up to assess the efficiency of the orthosis, and weigh the ergonomics of their use thereby enhancing adoption of the proposed orthotic solution.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, Active orthosis, Ergonomic assessment, Rehabilitation

EVALUATION ERGONOMIQUE D'UNE ORTHESE ACTIVE POUR LES PATIENTS DE LA MALADIE DE PARKINSON

Résumé

Le vieillissement de la population entraîne une hausse du nombre de cas de la maladie de Parkinson (MP). Ciblante le système nerveux, elle se manifeste principalement par des tremblements. Bien que ces derniers restent très handicapants pour effectuer des tâches quotidiennes, les patients doivent faire face à d'autres symptômes, comme la rigidité musculaire impactant la liberté de mouvement. Les causes biologiques de la maladie demeurent peu connues, de ce fait d'autres approches doivent être envisagées pour améliorer la condition de vie des patients.

Ce rapport décrit mon rôle au sein d'un laboratoire développant une orthèse active, dont la forme épouse celle de l'avant-bras de son utilisateur, afin de permettre le recouvrement de l'amplitude du poignet particulièrement affectée par la MP. L'objectif fut de faire de l'orthèse un outil exploitable et confortable, décrit ci-après comme ergonomique. Pour cela, sur un prototype déjà existant, des variables ergonomiques clés ont été étudiées, en particulier la stabilité, l'inertie relative (propre à chaque utilisateur) et l'altération de l'amplitude du mouvement. Ces dernières furent identifiées comme décrivant et impactant le comportement de l'orthèse. Cette étude pilote fut menée sur des sujets sains, et ses résultats ont permis un approfondissement de la connaissance du dispositif. Des méthodes de collectes de données et d'analyses furent mises au point et une évaluation des améliorations proposées fut réalisée à l'aide de scripts Matlab écrits par l'équipe de recherche, d'accéléromètres, de caméras infrarouges et d'acquisitions électromyographiques.

Grâce à un support imprimé en 3D à base d'un matériau polymère, l'amélioration de la stabilité du dispositif fut estimée à 77%. L'inertie relative fut déterminée de manière objective en concevant une méthode basée sur la comparaison de la Force Maximale Volontaire avec la force déployée lors de l'usage (ou non) de l'orthèse. Les données de l'expérience furent analysées avec succès via Matlab. Les résultats portant sur l'amplitude du mouvement sont eux attendus sous peu. L'équipe de recherche est désormais apte à considérer de nouveaux champs d'applications du dispositif, notamment pour les personnes ayant subi des accidents, brûlures au premier degré et AVC. Prochainement, des études sur des patients atteints de la MP seront entreprises à partir des protocoles expérimentaux développés au cours de l'étude pilote. Les patients se verront offrir un suivi personnalisé afin de conclure sur l'efficacité du dispositif.

Mots-clés : Maladie de Parkinson, Orthèse active, Evaluation ergonomique, Réhabilitation